

1 **End-to-end precision agriculture UAV-based** 2 **functionalities tailored to field characteristics**

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10 **Abstract** This paper presents a novel, low-cost, user-friendly Precision Agri-
11 culture platform that attempts to alleviate the drawbacks of limited bat-
12 tery life by carefully designing missions tailored to each field’s specific, time-
13 changing characteristics. The proposed system is capable of designing coverage
14 missions for any type of UAV, integrating field characteristics into the result-
15 ing trajectory, such as irregular field shape and obstacles. The collected images
16 are automatically processed to create detailed orthomosaics of the field and
17 extract the corresponding vegetation indices. A novel mechanism is then intro-
18 duced that automatically extracts possible problematic areas of the field and
19 subsequently designs a follow-up UAV mission to acquire extra information
20 on these regions. The toolchain is finished by using a deep learning module
21 that was made just for finding weeds in the close-examination flight. For the
22 development of such a deep-learning module, a new weed dataset from the
23 UAV’s perspective, which is publicly available for download, was collected
24 and annotated. All the above functionalities are enclosed in an open-source,
25 end-to-end platform, named Cognitive Operations of micro Flying vehicles
26 (CoFly). The effectiveness of the proposed system was tested and validated

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27 with extensive experimentation in agricultural fields with cotton in Larissa,
28 Greece during two different crop sessions.

29 **Keywords** Precision agriculture · UAVs · Coverage · Remote sensing ·
30 Site-specific inspection · Convolutional neural networks · Weed detection

31 1 Introduction

32 The course of human history can be characterized as a continuous struggle for
33 food, wealth distribution, and prosperity. The industrial revolution reformed
34 this process by setting the basis for mass and automated production. The
35 technological advancements in the sector of agriculture reflect this constant
36 human labor to guarantee adequate food resources. Nowadays, increasing the
37 global productivity and quality of food resources remains a challenging field
38 for humanity.

39 From the scope of economics, the primary sector embraces a wide part of it,
40 especially in the case of less heavily industrialized countries, where agriculture
41 remains a prime activity that leads to income and export revenue. Increasing
42 food production is primarily a prerequisite for human well-being but also eco-
43 nomic enhancement. Considering that apart from food resources, agriculture is
44 responsible also for the production of fabric, wood, paper, etc., increasing the
45 overall productivity rate remains a crucial issue from an economic perspective
46 also. However, while the production of all these viable goods is becoming more
47 and more overwhelming due to the continuous population growth [41], the al-
48 ready finite arable land is further being limited by extended farming that
49 deteriorates soil quality and increases the regions unsuitable for cultivation
50 [51]. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations
51 (*FAO*), it is estimated that annually around 20%-40% of any agricultural re-
52 gion is lost due to pests and diseases [21]. This cultivation regional loss along
53 with the constant need for increased productivity leads to excessive use of
54 pesticides that clearly threatens human health and pollutes the environment.

55 The worldwide prevalence of the aforementioned issues emerged a call for
56 immediate action and improvement in the agricultural sector [26], aiming to
57 develop more effective vegetative treatment strategies for enhancing the qual-
58 ity and quantity of crop yields. Towards this direction, utilizing remote sensing
59 technology holds the promise of a feasible solution to the aforementioned chal-
60 lenges. Processing of sensory data based on artificial intelligence and visual
61 analysis can provide propitious, so-called, Precision Agriculture (PA) tech-
62 niques for monitoring food, fabric, wood, etc. production. These PA techniques
63 focus on building systems for automation of important farming operations such
64 as monitoring the crop's growth and performance, assessing its fertilizer rate
65 and water level, etc. To achieve that, data acquisition from the agricultural
66 fields can provide information to the farmers regarding crop diseases, pest in-
67 festations, water stress, and other relevant issues that affect crop productivity.
68 By further processing the acquired sensory data, PA systems aim to correlate

69 production techniques with early crop management decisions to reduce agro-
70 chemical use and manage natural resources more efficiently while boosting
71 overall productivity.

72 However, particular challenges need to be met to allow the uptake of in-
73 novative technologies in smart farming to reach its promise [43]. The main
74 challenge when combining innovative technologies in precision agriculture is
75 the standardizing technology and the data synchronization of the involved
76 assets. Operating standards across different technologies may differ as many
77 commercial or non-commercial services adopted in the agricultural sector, have
78 been developed based on a completely different conceptual approach and are
79 intended to operate individually and only for a specific task (e.g., mission plan-
80 ning, image processing, etc.). This lack of interoperability causes monotonous
81 and time-consuming work for the operators since they have to manually feed
82 the output data from one subsystem to another. Another challenging task is
83 the data management plan. Even a small farm has thousands of data from
84 a crop session where information must be gathered to estimate and assess
85 its performance. Attempting to process and understand these data, without a
86 field service management system to store them, whether that is daily, monthly,
87 or seasonally, can be overwhelming for both agriculturalists and farmers. Last
88 but not least, the lack of scalability of many robot-related services, which are
89 designed only for scanning operations, are sure to end up with limited energy
90 autonomy while operating across hundreds of acres [9]. For precision agricul-
91 ture to take hold, any technological tool that is expected to assist farmers
92 must be scalable to the size of their needs, expectation, and farming oper-
93 ations. Conceptually, any agricultural software which is integrating robotics
94 and computer vision techniques must have a common holistic view of agricul-
95 tural processes enhancing crop yield management decisions by assisting even
96 non-expert users in proper manipulations.

97 In this direction, utilizing intelligence devices such as Unmanned Aerial
98 Vehicles (UAVs) have expanded the capabilities of PA techniques by enabling
99 flexibility, wieldy and adjustable to the case requirements solutions. Based
100 on that, integrated end-to-end platforms have been developed to automate
101 the procedures of UAV navigation, data collection, and processing for knowl-
102 edge extraction and decision support. Thanks to such platforms, common-
103 commercial UAVs have started to bring the agriculture production systems
104 into economic and environmental benefits, making productivity in the pri-
105 mary sector more sustainable. In the following subsection, an overview of the
106 important and recent related works regarding end-to-end platforms in the field
107 of agriculture is presented.

108 1.1 Related Work

109 Recent technological developments, a scale-up in sensor and UAV production
110 with a simultaneous decrease in cost, have given rise to a booming startup
111 industry. While in the beginning applications were limited to military use,

Application name	Flight planning	Health indices	Timeline view	Deep learning for weed detection	No-fly zones	Site-specific mission
Pix4D [35]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Drone Deploy [16]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Senterra FieldAgent [5]	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Agisoft [3]	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Botlink [12]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Blue River Technology [47]	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗
Christiansen et al. [15]	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
Primicerio et al. [37]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Uto et al. [48]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Vasudevan et al. [49]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Zheng et al. [53]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Karatzinis et al. [29]	✓	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗
CoFly	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Table 1: Competitiveness matrix listing commercially available products and research works, including this work (CoFly), comparing them with respect to different features.

112 soon enough a large number of industrial and civilian use cases emerged, one
 113 of them being precision agriculture.

114 According to a recent report [11], the agriculture drone market will be
 115 worth \$5.19 Billion by 2025, growing at an impressive Compound Annual
 116 Growth Rate (CAGR) of 31.1% from 2019. An overview and comparison
 117 among the most significant commercial agricultural products in terms of their
 118 farming technological features can be seen in the upper section of Table 1.
 119 Pix4D [35], DroneDeploy [16], and Senterra FieldAgent [5] are commercial
 120 drone mapping software which incorporate digital farming technologies, emerg-
 121 ing at precision agriculture and farming development. They can produce UAV
 122 flight paths, capture aerial photographs, visualize health indices, as well as
 123 provide a timeline view of previous field scans for continuous monitoring pur-
 124 poses. Agisoft Metashape [3] is advertised as a product for creating 3D maps
 125 using photogrammetry, including crop yield and plant health maps. Botlink
 126 [12] is a UAV-based agricultural software with an integrated flight planning
 127 framework that can provide high-definition 2-D and 3-D outputs as well as
 128 vegetation indices. While Blue River technology [47] is not a UAV technol-
 129 ogy company, but rather a provider of smart farm machines to manage crops
 130 at a plant level, their product is mention-worthy, as it uses computer vision
 131 and deep learning techniques to monitor each plant in the field individually, a
 132 feature which integrated UAV products are currently lacking.

133 Research-wise, a large number of UAV-based applications have been de-
 134 veloped, for a variety of agricultural practices, such as crop health and yield
 135 monitoring (second half of Table 1), making up the majority of agricultural
 136 applications due to the ease of use, portability, and economic viability com-
 137 pared to available commercial products, while others incorporate crop spraying
 138 techniques [19], [20], which are rather limited owing to the lower payloads that
 139 most autonomous UAVs can carry. According to a recent review paper [39],
 140 most of these developed systems use commercial software for 3D photogram-
 141 metry, visualization, and health index calculation (Pix4dMapper [35], Agisoft

142 Metashape [3]). In terms of contribution, these works mostly focus on improv-
143 ing specific workflows; for example, estimating the overall plant volume and
144 the soil surface for specific crop parcels [15]; monitoring and recording the
145 reflectance of the vegetation canopy [37]; estimation of chlorophyll levels in
146 rice paddies by evaluating vegetation indices derived by hyperspectral data
147 [48]; inspecting periodically the status of crops while obtaining multiple im-
148 ages of them and calculating various indices, as well as pH level and acidity
149 [49]; evaluating the capabilities of a hyperspectral camera in identifying the
150 nitrogen status in rice crops [53]; monitoring and mapping vineyards as well as
151 identification of discontinuous crop rows based on image stitching and health
152 index computation [29].

153 From a motion planning view, a great majority of bespoke systems use
154 ROS framework [38], while others use Ardupilot Mission Planner software [8],
155 Pix4DCapture [35] or any other software compatible with the drone. While
156 the aforementioned UAV flight planning software is broadly used and open-
157 source, they do not offer capabilities that fit each field's characteristics such
158 as no-fly zones and automatic UAV-based weed detection. A deeper look into
159 available open-source UAV flight controllers and flight simulators [17], reveals
160 that there are ample options for flight control and mission planning [6], [30],
161 [4] however, none of these extend their capability beyond that to offer data
162 post-processing capabilities.

163 Overall, several research works include remote sensing capabilities for a
164 variety of UAV-based applications in precision agriculture. Despite their effec-
165 tiveness and usefulness, the main drawback of these systems is the fact that
166 are intended for specific tasks and not for a holistic view of agricultural pro-
167 cesses. For example, some of them focus more on flight planning and health
168 index calculation without having an integrated system including a friendly
169 user interface that eases and automate the utilization of the UAVs [37], [48],
170 [49], [29]. Some others utilize separate commercial software for UAV planning
171 in terms of data acquisition and crop health index computation, making their
172 customization in agriculture applications difficult as they require some exper-
173 tise in order to be consolidated and manageable as an overall system [15],
174 [53]. Besides, utilizing commercial products might be non-affordable as some
175 of them establish a price according to daily or monthly use. Finally, almost
176 none of the aforementioned commercial or research works incorporate no-fly
177 zones inside the area of interest but support only generic coverage missions
178 which are universally applied to all crop fields (no site-specific missions).

179 1.2 Contributions

180 In this work, we propose a holistic approach focusing in a high-level, user-
181 friendly, and centralized platform developed to perform precision agriculture
182 practices based on UAV functionalities, optimized for real-life use and specifi-
183 cally tailored to each field's characteristics. The proposed platform aims at
184 enhancing the software-dependent system abilities in various robot-related re-

Fig. 1: CoFly’s high-level architecture.

185 search areas while the hardware requirements are kept at the most significant
 186 so that the cost could be kept at low levels.

187 In a nutshell, the overall workflow of the proposed platform is illustrated
 188 in Figure 1 and consists of the following steps.

- 189 1. *UAV flight planning*: Initially, a Region of Interest (ROI) with a possible
 190 no-fly zone along with the UAV’s flight planning parameters is defined.
 191 Given this user-defined information, the CoFly framework extracts an auto-
 192 mated mission for the drone mapping project where it can be monitored
 193 live through the smartphone.
- 194 2. *Computation and display of health indices*: Each frame per second an aerial
 195 image taken by the UAV is uploaded to CoFly software for processing.
 196 When the mission ends, all the collected visual data are merged and provide
 197 an orthomosaic as an accurate map of the ROI. Given the orthomosaic,
 198 several Vegetation Indices (VIs) maps for assessing crop health are available
 199 to display.
- 200 3. *Site-specific mission*: CoFly software classifies the available VI maps and
 201 estimates the center of the problematic areas which are considered essential
 202 for further processing and marked as Points of Interest. On top of that, an
 203 automated site-specific mission with low altitude focused on site-specific
 204 treatment and weed detection is designed to provide a more thorough in-
 205 spection of these problematic locations.

206 Although several UAV platforms are available and capable of providing
 207 high-end, informative representations of the field, all of them are severely re-
 208 stricted by the hardware (mainly battery capabilities) of the deployed UAV,
 209 leading to limited energy autonomy and operational time. CoFly system aims
 210 to alleviate this drawback by utilizing an extra automatic way of creating also
 211 precision UAV flights considering the extracted field-specific knowledge (site-

specific mission). In other words, the idea of this added feature is to avoid an over-detailed scanning of the whole field, but rather to combine a quick overview with cognition capabilities to accommodate solutions and alleviate the drawbacks of the UAV's limited battery life while operating across hundreds of acres improving, thus, the operating time and energy efficiency of the monitoring process. More specifically, the novelty of this paper lies in a holistic framework for precision agriculture integrating the following unique characteristics and custom software solutions:

- Low-cost deployment by using off-the-shelf drones,
- Easy-to-use and compatible with any commercial UAV,
- Mobility and data synchronization across devices,
- UAV built-in flight planning for automated crop monitoring,
- Integrated image processing functionalities for orthomosaic extraction and vegetation health estimation,
- UAV built-in site-specific mission based on the extracted knowledge and combined with incorporated deep learning model for weed detection,
- No-fly zones/Obstacle avoidance,
- Timeline view for storing information according to the year's harvest.

The proposed platform aims at providing the operator/farmer with a cost-effective and end-to-end integrated system to accomplish autonomous tasks that were used to be completed manually (e.g. crop growth monitoring). Besides, it will play a supportive role in decision-making objectives (e.g. possible weed infestations) enhancing crop yield management decisions by assisting non-expert users in proper manipulations. A comparison of the main features, of all available platforms, as long as the advantages of the CoFly approach are presented in Table 1.

To the best of our knowledge, CoFly is the first to integrate (i) mission planning supporting no-fly-zones and obstacles, (ii) plant health index calculation-visualization, (iii) weed detection using deep learning, with (iv) a user-friendly and intuitive graphical user interface. All of the aforementioned services are build upon modules of enhanced and properly modified well-established methodologies, providing unique characteristics toward a fully functional end-to-end field service management system.

Our work is an open source alternative, directly comparable to commercially available platforms, aiming to maximize the usage of PA by non experienced in UAV flight end-users. At the same time, we offer the research community a tool to develop and test custom solutions for specific agricultural applications. The overall CoFly ecosystem is open-source and publicly available¹ to the community.

¹ <https://github.com/CoFly-Project>

1.3 Paper Structure

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the translation of a general coverage motion planning framework to an optimization problem and describes the developed algorithm for tackling such a problem. In this section, a simulated evaluation is performed in different scenarios to adequately analyze the performance of the developed algorithm. Section 3 presents the proposed methodologies for extracting vegetative knowledge regarding the crop’s health status along with a pixel-wise pipeline for detecting possible problematic locations. Section 4 describes the proposed motion planning algorithm for dealing with the site-specific inspection and presents the weed detection module by using deep learning methods. Section 5 presents an overview of the graphical user interface and displays the overall workflow for the system’s integration. Section 6 includes the real-life experiments along with the visual results and finally, in Section 7, concluding remarks are given.

2 UAV Coverage Path Planning

2.1 Problem Formulation

For the purpose of covering a continuous area, it is essential to deploy a method that provides safe and efficient paths while ensuring complete coverage of the agricultural field. To efficiently cope with challenges faced in real-world scenarios, one should analyze all the aspects that govern Coverage Path Planning (CPP) problems [24]. With the term CPP, we refer to the task of determining a path that passes through all the points of an area while avoiding any No-Fly Zones (NFZs)/Obstacles possible defined within the operational area.

In this paper, the proposed platform deals with the problem of designing a path given:

A. Field-based info:

- a *user-defined polygon* (A) which contains a series of points that define the agricultural field to be scanned,
- a *user-defined sub-polygon* (\mathcal{O}), if needed, representing the NFZs/Obstacles within A .

B. UAV-based info:

- the *scanning density*, in meters, representing the distance between two adjacent flight path lines,
- the *flight direction*, in degrees, defining the direction of the path within A ,
- the *flight altitude* of the UAV for the mission,
- the *speed* of the UAV for the mission.

The objective is to compile all this user-defined information and extract a set of coordinates, representing a safe and efficient path, so as to provide a complete coverage of the A . Note that the defined problem does not assume

291 any type of UAV, but rather adapts to each UAV's capabilities by tuning the
 292 UAV-based info (as defined previously) accordingly.

293 2.1.1 Field Approximation on Grid

294 To begin with, let us assume that the agricultural field that needs to be covered
 295 has an arbitrary shape and is constrained within a two-dimensional polygon
 296 A defined by a set of coordinates (x, y) . As a first step, A must be represented
 297 as a grid. For the grid approximation, A is decomposed into a finite set of
 298 equal cells which do not overlap while filling the entire area of A . The number
 299 of these cells represents the required spatial resolution of the UAV's collected
 300 images for monitoring crop growth. It should be noted that in the proposed
 301 platform, the spatial level resolution can be specified through the values of the
 302 *flight altitude* and *scanning density*.

303 The grid representation of A is described as follows:

$$\mathcal{U} := \{x, y : x \in [1, rows], y \in [1, cols]\} \quad (1)$$

304 where *rows*, *cols* enumerate the rows and columns after the grid discretiza-
 305 tion of the terrain to be covered. Apparently, the size of the grid \mathcal{U} is given by
 306 $n = rows \times cols$.

307 During cellular decomposition, we also assume that there are n_o obstacles
 308 at the size of a cell placed in several known positions. The set of these obstacles
 309 are described as follows:

$$\mathcal{O} := \{(x, y) \in \mathcal{U} : (x, y) \text{ is occupied}\} \quad (2)$$

310 where each cell that corresponds to any obstructed area on the actual field
 311 is marked as occupied. Evidently, the number of cells that need to be covered
 312 are reduced to $l = n - n_o$

313 Therefore, the set of unoccupied cells that should be covered is described
 314 as follows:

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{U} \setminus \mathcal{O} \quad (3)$$

315 2.1.2 Nodes Placement

316 Having defined the operational area \mathcal{U} , we proceed by defining the allowed UAV
 317 movements, from each grid cell within \mathcal{L} , to fully cover an agricultural field A .
 318 To achieve that, an undirected weighted graph $G = (V, E)$ is introduced. Each
 319 vertex $V \in G$ is placed in the center of each grid cell of set \mathcal{L} and represented
 320 as a node. The edges among these nodes denote the allowed movements of the
 321 UAV when navigating inside \mathcal{L} . Generally, each node is connected with four
 322 adjacent nodes following the Von Neumann neighborhood [36]. Nodes that are

323 placed on the boundaries of the operational area or are adjacent to an obstacle
 324 have less edges.

325 definition

326 **Definition 1** Two nodes $u_{(x_i, y_i)}, v_{(x_j, y_j)} \in G$ are consider to be *adjacent* if:

$$\|(x_i, y_i)\| - \|(x_j, y_j)\| = s_d \quad (4)$$

327 where s_d defines the value of *scanning density* in meters.

328 **Definition 2** A *valid path* of length m is considered any sequence of nodes

$$\mathcal{X} = \{l_1, l_2, \dots, l_m\} \quad (5)$$

329 where $\exists E(l_i, l_{i+1}) \forall i \in [1, l_{m-1}]$.

330 In other words, the set of $(V, E) \in G$ within \mathcal{L} provides us with informa-
 331 tion corresponding to a sequence of adjacent nodes allocated in the center of
 332 the unoccupied cells. Consequently, if a series of nodes follows Def. 2 could
 333 constitute a *valid path* that passes through all the points of \mathcal{U} while avoid-
 334 ing obstacles. Hence, G to provide a *valid path* specifically tailored to each
 335 field's characteristics is also directly related to the characteristic hyperparam-
 336 eter *flight direction*. Modifying the flight direction feature intends to optimize
 337 the node's placement inside \mathcal{U} to create a more favorable -in terms of coverage-
 338 representation of G .

339 The key idea is the rotation of each node within the grid \mathcal{U} by an angle
 340 ϑ in a counter-clockwise direction around a center-point. Given the desired
 341 angle ϑ determined by the *flight direction* value, the rotation of each node is
 342 defined by the following equations:

$$x_{new} = c_x + (x - c_x) \cdot \cosh(\vartheta) - (y - c_y) \cdot \sinh(\vartheta) \quad (6)$$

$$y_{new} = c_y + (x - c_x) \cdot \sinh(\vartheta) + (y - c_y) \cdot \cosh(\vartheta) \quad (7)$$

343 where the following constraints are hold:

- 344 – A is defined in a two-dimensional space,
- 345 – the center-point c_x, c_y is defined as the center of A ,
- 346 – $(x, y) \forall V \in G$ are in the form of Cartesian plane,
- 347 – ϑ , which controls the rotation of G over \mathcal{U} , is in range $[0, 360^\circ]$.

348 Modifying the flight's direction, there might appear more favorable config-
 349 urations of G inside \mathcal{U} , where the number of nodes within \mathcal{L} is greater. Such
 350 configurations are more likely to provide paths that achieve a higher percent-
 351 age of coverage for the given A . It must be emphasized that the x_{new}, y_{new}
 352 variables are rotating with respect to the user's desired *scanning density*.

2.1.3 Optimization Problem

Given the mathematical description presented above, the problem of finding a minimum size of a collection of edges (UAV movements) that cover all the vertices of the graph can be translated into the minimization of the covering path \mathcal{X} , so as,

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{minimize} && m \\ & \text{subject to} && E \subseteq \{l_i, l_{i+1}\}, i = 1, \dots, l_{m-1} \\ & && \mathcal{X} \supseteq \mathcal{L} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

- m is a positive integer which denotes the cardinality of set \mathcal{X} ,
- $l \in \mathcal{L}$ is the number of unoccupied cells,
- E is a set of edges-movements,
- \mathcal{X} is a *valid path*.

2.2 Navigation Algorithm

Having illustrated all the prime features that constitute a completely safe and efficient path, we proceed to present a navigation algorithm in steps, as sketched in Figure 2, for solving the optimization problem of (8). The navigation system that we propose in this paper, utilizes the Spanning Tree Algorithm [23] which deploys an off-line coverage path planning algorithm as the UAV covers any arbitrary shape, while knowing in advance any related information about the location of the NFZs/Obstacles. Conceptually, this algorithm along with the equations of 2.1 tackles the aforementioned challenges and achieves the overall mission objectives within five distinct steps.

Algorithm 1 outlines in pseudo-code the key steps of the proposed navigation algorithm.

Step 1. As a first step, in lines 1 and 2, the user’s input data A and \mathcal{O} are transformed from WGS84-EPSG:4326 into WGS84-EPSG:3857 [44]. For ease of understanding, let us analyze the usage of this transformation.

To start with, EPSG standard codes are used as Spatial Reference System Identifiers for map datasets. EPSG:4326 projects the map dataset in a coordinate system on the surface of a sphere while EPSG:3857 projects the map dataset in a coordinate system on the surface of a square. The reason why this transformation is needed is because A and \mathcal{O} are initially defined in a set of latitude/longitude pairs while *scanning density* is defined in meters. In latitude/longitude (EPSG:4326), distances are not measured in meters, but rather in decimal degrees. To efficiently deal with these challenges, a Web-Pseudo Mercator projection (EPSG:3857) was used to project these latitude/longitude pairs in a square shape which supports a metric system in meters. This suitable projection was used for dealing with the above aforementioned mathematical descriptions of 2.1, extract the path points, and project them back to latitude/longitude pairs.

Fig. 2: Spanning-Tree Coverage algorithm main steps and terminology.

391 Having transformed the input coordinates A, \mathcal{O} to a Cartesian Plane shape,
 392 in lines 3-10, the entire area of A is grouped into large square-shaped cells,
 393 each of which is either entirely blocked or entirely unblocked, as shown in Fig
 394 2(a). It must be noted, as the only algorithm's requirement, that the areas
 395 which include stationary obstacles within the grid cannot be smaller than a
 396 large square-shaped cell.

397 *Step 2.* In lines 11-21, after the discretization of the field, every unoccupied
 398 large square-shaped cell is translated into a node and for each pair of nodes,
 399 a number (the weight) is assigned to each edge. These nodes-edges, regulated
 400 by the flight direction feature, form the graph $G = (V, E)$ which defines the
 401 allowed movements of the UAV (Figure 2(b)).

402 *Step 3.* As a next step (line 23), a graph minimization methodology by
 403 using Kruskal's algorithm [32] is applied in the previously formed graph G as
 404 illustrated in Fig 2(c). The resulting minimum spanning tree (MST) contains
 405 the minimum number of edges among all nodes (allowed movements) so that
 406 G remains fully connected. Figure 2(d) graphically depicts the resulting MST
 407 above the original discrete area of Fig 2(b).

408 *Step 4.* The UAV, then, to cover the area of interest circumnavigates the
 409 MST [28] in a clockwise direction along the subdivided subcells of line 22, as
 410 illustrated in Figure 2(e). The circumnavigation of the spanning tree (line

Algorithm 1 Trajectory Planner²

Input: $A = \{Lat_A, Lon_A\}$, $\mathcal{O} = \{Lat_{\mathcal{O}}, Lon_{\mathcal{O}}\}$, *scanning density*, *flight direction*
Output: $\mathcal{X} = \{Lat_{\mathcal{X}}, Lon_{\mathcal{X}}\}$ ▷ Solution of (8)

- 1: $\{x_A, y_A\} \leftarrow$ Project $\{Lat_A, Lon_A\}$ from EPSG:4326-to-3857
- 2: $\{x_{\mathcal{O}}, y_{\mathcal{O}}\} \leftarrow$ Project $\{Lat_{\mathcal{O}}, Lon_{\mathcal{O}}\}$ from EPSG:4326-to-3857
- 3: $x \leftarrow \min(x_A)$
- 4: **while** $x \leq \max(x_A)$ **do** ▷ Iterate over 2D area
- 5: $y \leftarrow \min(y_A)$
- 6: **while** $y \leq \max(y_A)$ **do**
- 7: $y \leftarrow y + \textit{scanning density}$
- 8: $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow (x, y)$ ▷ Grid representation of A (1)
- 9: $x \leftarrow x + \textit{scanning density}$
- 10: $\mathcal{L} \leftarrow$ Discard every cell in \mathcal{U} according to (2)
- 11: $V \leftarrow \{(x, y) \mid (x, y) \in \mathcal{L}\}$
- 12: **for each** node $\in V$ **do**
- 13: **if** Def. 1 is **True** **then**
- 14: $E \leftarrow \{(u, \nu, \textit{weight} = 0)\}$
- 15: **else**
- 16: $E \leftarrow \{(u, \nu, \textit{weight} = 1)\}$
- 17: $G \leftarrow (V, E)$ ▷ Undirected weighted graph
- 18: **if** *flight direction* $\neq 0$ **then** ▷ Node rotation
- 19: **for each** $x, y \in V$ **do**
- 20: $x_{new} \leftarrow (6)$
- 21: $y_{new} \leftarrow (7)$
- 22: $\mathcal{U} \leftarrow$ Subdivide every cell $\in \mathcal{L}$ in four identical subcells
- 23: MST \leftarrow Construct a minimal spanning tree for G by using any minimum-spanning-tree algorithm, MST $\in G$
- 24: A starting cell S $\in \mathcal{L}$ as the initial position of UAV
- 25: $\{x_{sub}, y_{sub}\} \leftarrow$ Traverse MST in a clock-wise direction through subcells of line 22, starting from cell S. Halt when S is encountered again.
- 26: $\{Lat_{\mathcal{X}}, Lon_{\mathcal{X}}\} \leftarrow$ Project $\{x_{sub}, y_{sub}\}$ from EPSG:3857-to-4326
- 27: Smooth the trajectory in turns with *corner radius*

411 25) generates a simple closed path $\mathcal{X} = \{(Lat_1, Lon_1), (Lat_2, Lon_2), \dots,$
 412 $(Lat_m, Lon_m)\}$, where m denotes the number of waypoints, (Figure 2(f)).

413 *Step 5.* Once Algorithm 1 determines a path \mathcal{X} , in line 27, a smoothing
 414 hyperparameter called *corner radius* is introduced and applied in turns. Figure
 415 3 illustrates the path smoothing process with the black line indicating the path
 416 \mathcal{X} generated in *Step 4* while the blue line indicates an *optimal* \mathcal{X} -in terms of
 417 covering time- solution after the applied smoothing process.

418 Having defined the navigation algorithm, let us provide some necessary pre-
 419 liminaries about the flight hyperparameters (*flight altitude*, *scanning density*,
 420 *flight direction*, *corner radius*, *speed*) and how they affect the overall quality of
 421 aerial mapping. An important analysis of those hyperparameters is analyzed
 422 below:

423 ***Flight altitude.*** Low flight altitudes yield the highest resolution and best
 424 precision in mapping with more matched features per image. In contrast, fly-
 425 ing at a higher altitude covers more space and allows the capture of common
 426 unique features in multiple images which can be useful when mapping areas

² <https://github.com/CoFly-Project/Waypoint-Trajectory-Planning>

Fig. 3: Path smoothing process regulated by the hyperparameter *corner radius*.

427 with homogeneous imagery. Consequently, *flight altitude* determines the overlap
 428 between two corresponding images in the same flight path line as sketched
 429 in Figure 4(a) (*frontlap*).

430 **Scanning density.** In the proposed CPP method, the distance between
 431 two sequential trajectories is determined by the value of *scanning density*. As a
 432 result, this distance can control the overlap between images from two adjacent
 433 flight path lines as sketched in Figure 4(b) (*sidelap*).

Fig. 4: Overlap settings regulated by the hyperparameters *flight altitude* and *scanning density*. Subfigure (a) illustrates the overlap between two sequential images on the same flight path line. Subfigure (b) illustrates the overlap between two sequential images in adjacent parallel flight path lines.

434 **Flight direction.** Using the flight direction feature allows you to change
 435 the direction that your drone flies and ensure that the extracted path pattern
 436 is tailored to the field. Figure 5 illustrates an example where the flight direction
 437 feature is applied to a specific *complex-shaped* polygon.

438 **Corner radius.** Speed deviation and 90° degree turn on the spot maximize
 439 the flight time of the mission and can lead in many cases to inefficient missions.
 440 Controlling indirectly the *corner radius* hyperparameter minimizes the flight
 441 time by allowing smooth turns where the UAV, during a turning point, does
 442 not make a 90° degree turn on the spot but rather moves along the perimeter
 443 of a circle with a radius equal to the value of the *corner radius*. Note that the
 444 value of the *corner radius* should fluctuate at low levels e.g. 0.5-1m to minimize
 445 the aircraft's deceleration at the turning points and at the same time avoid
 446 deviating from the resulted coverage path \mathcal{X} .

Fig. 5: Flight path direction regulated by the *flight direction* hyperparameter based on node setup.

447 **Speed.** Last but not least, *speed* controls the speed at which the UAV
 448 flies during a mission. The UAV's flight speed varies according to the flight
 449 planning parameters and image overlap settings.

450 Adjusting the aforementioned hyperparameters to the crop yield can lead
 451 to an optimized setup by generating a path pattern tailored to each field's
 452 characteristics and optimize the chance of generating high-resolution maps.

453 2.3 Simulated Evaluation

454 To assess the performance of the proposed navigation algorithm to the quan-
 455 tity of coverage and the overall quality of paths, two different metrics are
 456 considered. The first metric *Percentage of Coverage (PoC)* is for the accuracy
 457 in terms of coverage and the second metric *Estimated Flight Time (EFT)* is
 458 for the efficiency in terms of coverage time.

459 The metric *PoC* intends to represent the percentage of coverage directly
 460 matched to a path \mathcal{X} within A . Given the problem definition, *PoC* is defined
 461 as follows:

$$PoC = \frac{n_A}{n_{A_{max}}} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

462 where n_A denotes the number of nodes placed inside a polygon A which
 463 will be used for the MST construction and $n_{A_{max}}$ denotes the theoretically
 464 maximum number of nodes that could fit inside a given polygon A . Thus
 465 given A and *scanning density*, $n_{A_{max}}$ is formulated as follows:

$$n_{A_{max}} = \frac{A (m^2)}{\text{scanning density}^2 (m^2)} \quad (10)$$

466 where A is defined in m^2 and *scanning density* is defined in *meters* in the
 467 x-axis and the y-axis, respectively (Algorithm 1, lines 7 & 9).

468 The second metric *EFT* intends to represent the estimation time, in min-
 469 utes, for the UAV to follow a path. As to covering time, the *EFT* is determined
 470 by the simulation time.

471 RotorS UAV [22] simulator framework was utilized to test and evaluate
 472 the proposed navigation algorithm. RotorS is an open-source, simulator for
 473 unmanned aerial vehicles based on the Robot Operating System (ROS) and
 474 the Gazebo 3D robotics simulator. All the experiments were carried out in
 475 the waypoint-navigator package [34] of the aforementioned simulator, which
 476 is a high-level waypoint-following package that simulates a trajectory through
 477 a list of waypoints formatted in WGS84-EPSG:4326. For the representation
 478 and visualization of the trajectories we used the RViz (Robot Visualization)
 479 program [45], an auxiliary tool for visualizing our waypoint data in a real
 480 domain. RotorS was hosted in a common laptop (Intel Core i7-8750H CPU)
 481 with Ubuntu 16.04 LTS and a combination of v7.7/Kinetic as a version of
 482 Gazebo and ROS package, respectively.

483 For the evaluation of the proposed method, a set of 6 generated polygons
 484 is used. This set includes *complex-shaped* and *non complex-shaped* polygons,
 485 with or without obstacles. The simulations were carried out with the default
 486 UAV model of RotorS equipped with GPS and IMU sensors. Moreover, it is
 487 assumed that the UAV is initially located at (Lat_1, Lon_1) of each simulated
 488 trajectory \mathcal{X} . For all sets, the proposed method was executed with fixed *flight*
 489 *altitude* and *speed* of 100 m and 3 m/s, respectively. Additional information
 490 associated to each scenario is presented in Table 2. It should be noted that
 491 each scenario was designed in such a way to demonstrate the performance
 492 of Algorithm 1 and test the effect of the *flight direction* and *corner radius*
 493 hyperparameters on the resulting path in terms of coverage percentage and
 494 time. The rest of the hyperparameters were not evaluated in RotorS as they
 495 do not directly affect the path pattern but rather the image overlap settings.

Scenario #	Area (acres)	NFZs/Obstacles (acres)	Scanning density	Flight direction	Corner radius (m)	EFT [22]	PoC
1	7.39	0	30	0	0	8:31.394	93.31%
2	7.39	0	30	20	0	8:94.510	96.32%
3	7.39	0	30	20	0.5	8:44.197	96.32%
4	10.65	0	35	0	0	10:88.281	99.48%
5	10.65	0.65	35	0	0	10:11.192	96.96%
6	10.65	0.65	35	0	0.5	9:53.855	96.96%

Table 2: Evaluation metrics based on scenarios description.

496 For each scenario, Algorithm 1 was employed to calculate the respective
 497 UAV path to solve optimization problem (8) aiming at maximizing the *PoC*
 498 while minimizing the *EFT*. The visualization of the produced trajectories \mathcal{X}
 499 for each scenario along with their corresponding performance is presented in
 500 Figure 6 and the last two columns of Table 2.

501 The results of the evaluation procedure are reported and analyzed in the
 502 following paragraphs.

503 In Scenario #1, 31 nodes with *flight direction* = 0, are selected for the MST
 504 construction as important regions of interest for the UAV. In Scenario #2, by
 505 only modifying the flight's direction, the navigation algorithm finds a more

Fig. 6: Path visualizations in RViz. Effect of the hyperparameters *flight direction* & *corner radius* on the resulting path according to each scenario description.

506 profitable -in terms of coverage- configuration of \mathcal{U} inside A with 32 nodes
 507 selected as important regions of interest. As presented in the last column of
 508 Table 2, the resulting path \mathcal{X} of Scenario #2 in comparison to Scenario #1 is
 509 more *optimal* in terms of coverage. However, due to the increasing number of
 510 waypoints, the flight time of Scenario #2 is greater than Scenario #1. Hence,
 511 Scenario #3 is considered to demonstrate the effectiveness of smoothing the
 512 trajectory in turns. As presented in the *EFT* column of Table 2, by tuning the
 513 *corner radius*, the overall flight time of the resulting path \mathcal{X} of Scenario #3 is
 514 decreasing in contrast to Scenario #2, providing thus the exact percentage of
 515 coverage. While Scenarios #1, #2 and #3 are demonstrated in *complex-shaped*
 516 *polygon*, in Scenario #4 when in *non-complex polygon* even without optimizing
 517 the nodes placement within \mathcal{U} (*flight direction* = 0), Algorithm 1 achieves a
 518 high percentage of coverage. In addition, the effectiveness of Algorithm 1 is
 519 also demonstrated in Scenarios #5 and #6. In both Scenarios, 27 nodes were
 520 selected for the MST construction while 5 nodes were considered to contain
 521 NFZs/Obstacles. For both scenarios the resulting path either with smoothing
 522 or not achieves an average *PoC* above 96%.

523 Overall, the developed algorithm designs the UAV paths, in such a way as
 524 to achieve high *PoC* both in complex and non-complex fields while keeping
 525 the flight time as minimum as possible, enabling the prolonged utilization of
 526 the UAV in the agricultural application.

3 Location Estimates for Crop Health Monitoring

To maximize the system's usability and incorporate novel and cognitive functionalities, the framework involves sequentially executed processes that eventually improve the crop monitoring process. After the execution of the generic coverage mission presented in Section 2, a set of RGB georeferenced images covering the whole field has been collected. This set comprises the base of the subsequent processing procedures aiming at i) extracting knowledge regarding the crop's health status and ii) providing identified locations over the field that correspond to the centers of detected problematic areas. The following sub-sections analyze the integrated procedures.

3.1 Image Stitching Process

The aim of the current module is to merge the collected visual data and provide an orthomosaic as an accurate map of the examined area. Towards this direction an appropriate tool for image stitching has been deployed which is based on the following process:

1. Firstly, the telemetry from the metadata of each image is extracted in order to speed up and improve the accuracy of the stitching process.
2. Then, a sparse point cloud is generated with the Open Structure from Motion (OpenSfM) [2] library.
3. The generated point cloud is transformed to triangle meshes via the Poisson Surface Reconstruction [10] method.
4. The triangle meshes are textured over by selecting appropriate patches from the acquired images generating the georeferenced orthoimage.

The above process can be implemented with the OpenDroneMap (ODM) [1] toolkit. In Figure 7 the generated orthophoto of an examined area is demonstrated. The outcome of the aforementioned stitching process constitutes a comprehensive map-quality representation of the field and can be further processed as a whole, to extract qualitative features, such as an estimation of the vegetation health, and provide the end-user an overview of the crop status.

3.2 Vegetation Indices (VIs)

To enhance the capacities of the proposed framework toward a cognitive precision agriculture system, the previously defined stitched map of the under-study field is further processed to estimate the vegetation's health. Considered as the main objective and motivation of the proposed system, crop health estimation prerequisites the utilization of such metrics. These estimates, widely known as Vegetation Indices (VIs), are strictly dependent on the available sensor that is equipped on the deployed UAVs. Relevant sensors involve operations under either the visual or a wider light spectrum which eventually is used to identify defects and problematic crop areas.

Fig. 7: Extracted orthomosaic map of an examined area.

566 The use of a multi-spectral camera would provide accurate and more mean-
 567 ingful data for estimating plant health via the calculation of some pertinent
 568 VIs. Despite their widest exploitation and their increased performance in pre-
 569 cision agriculture applications, deploying a multi-spectral sensor will signifi-
 570 cantly increase the total cost while technical restrictions might be inserted such
 571 as a considerably lower acquisition rate. On the other hand, employing off-the-
 572 shelf UAVs utilizing RGB cameras consists of a low-cost and easy-to-deploy
 573 solution. To this end, VIs focused on the visual spectrum were incorporated as
 574 the usage of a visual camera is more flexible and affordable. Therefore, multi-
 575 ple VIs were adopted and developed to cover the majority of aspects that are
 576 related to crop health. The employed RGB-based VIs are presented in Table 3.

Vegetation Index	Name	Formula	References
VARI	Visible Atmospheric Resistant Index	$\frac{G-R}{G+R-B}$	[25]
GLI	Green Leaf Index	$\frac{2 \times G - R - B}{2 \times G + R + B}$	[33]
NGRDI	Normalized Green Red Difference Index	$\frac{G-R}{G+R}$	[27]
NGBDI	Normalized Green Blue Difference Index	$\frac{G-B}{G+B}$	[52]

Table 3: Vegetation Indices (VIs)

577 Each one of the four selected VIs represents the actual reflectance of the
 578 field's vegetation in different color bands and thus, it can reflect different

579 measures of crop health. More specifically, the Visual Atmospheric Resistance
 580 Index (*VARI*) [25], originally designed for satellite imagery, considers the blue
 581 light scattering as the blue spectrum travels in smaller wavelengths. On the
 582 contrary, Green Leaf Index (*GLI*) [33] was proposed to measure wheat cover
 583 and all main color bands are considered in a weighted approach. Similarly, Nor-
 584 malized Green-Red Difference Index (*NGRDI*) [27] is obtained by calculating
 585 the reflectance of the green and the red zone of the electromagnetic spectrum.
 586 A similar approach is adopted for the Normalized Green-Blue Difference Index
 587 (*NGBDI*) [52] nonetheless, the estimation relies on the reflectance of the green
 588 and the blue zone. These VIs were selected as an established choice capable
 589 to reflect and represent the under-study agriculture-related issues.

590 The estimated VI maps are defined within a limited range and displayed
 591 to the operator by utilizing a red-green color-map by using the appropriate
 592 scale, as demonstrated in Figures 8(a)-8(d). Since each calculated VI reflects
 593 different aspects of the visual light that is incorporated, the corresponding
 594 visualization for every VI is unique as different aspects of plant health are
 595 assumed.

Fig. 8: Image representations of the four calculated VIs. Lower index values are colored with red tones while higher index values correspond to green tones.

596 3.3 Location Extraction of Problematic Areas

597 The extracted VIs image representations can provide the end-user, with a con-
 598 crete overview of the crop's health. Yet, to automate the procedure, individual
 599 field regions that present poor conditions, in terms of vegetation health, have
 600 to be defined. This module aims to detect these problematic areas and feed
 601 their location to the site-specific mission module for a targeted, on-the-spot,
 602 inspection.

603 The significance of VIs is not only their ability to visualize the health status
 604 of the crop but also the quantification of this status by assigning a single
 605 value to each pixel of the processed image, usually, in the range $[-1, 1]$. Based
 606 on that, a pixel-wise processing pipeline has been developed to detect these
 607 regions where the corresponding index value is low and thus can be considered
 608 problematic. The deployed module consists of the following processing steps:

Fig. 9: Demonstration of the processing pipeline for the problematic areas identification. Initially the index array is (a) binary thresholded, then (b) connected component analysis is conducted to detect the center of mass of every problematic regions, finally (c) K-Means clustering is employed to estimate the centers of wider problematic areas.

- 609 1. Outlier detection
- 610 2. Binary thresholding
- 611 3. Connected components detection
- 612 4. Centers of mass calculation
- 613 5. Centers aggregation

614 Although the typical range of the presented VIs is $[-1, 1]$, in real-world
 615 cases the actual range can differ significantly and values close to the typical
 616 extrema can be considered outliers. Towards this direction, initial filtering of
 617 the index array outliers takes place. At first, the histogram of the index array
 618 is calculated. Assuming that k_1 is the first histogram's bin corresponding to
 619 the interval $[-1, -0.9]$, in case the frequency of this bin is smaller than 5% of
 620 N , where N is the number of the pixels corresponding to the entire field region,
 621 then the values belonging on the specific bin range are considered outliers and
 622 -0.9 is the actual minimum (notated as min) of the processed index array. The
 623 process is repeated for the next bin until the outlier criterion is not satisfied.
 624 A similar approach is applied to estimate the maximum value (max).

625 Next, binary thresholding is applied to separate the problematic areas from
 626 the healthy ones. As problematic areas are considered those with pixel values
 627 in the range $[min, t]$, where t is the binary threshold equal to $t = min +$
 628 $0.25(max - min)$. Although it is established that t is equal to the quarter-half
 629 of the VI's actual range, one could fine-tune this value manually to achieve
 630 better, crop-oriented performance. In Figure 9(a) the corresponding binary
 631 image acquired by thresholding the VARI index of Figure 8(a) is depicted.
 632 Afterward, a connected components analysis is employed to detect connected
 633 components on the binary image that correspond to a single problematic area.
 634 For every detected area, the center of mass is calculated leading to a set of
 635 points, as presented in Figure 9(b).

636 These center points are considered the destination points where the site-
 637 specific mission has to take place, to provide a more thorough inspection re-
 638 garding the low health conditions of the specific area. Yet, a large number of
 639 waypoints is usually prohibitive, since the flight time of a conventional drone
 640 is not adequate to operate in all these individual areas. Furthermore, there
 641 are cases where neighboring problematic areas can be considered as parts of
 642 a wider area that can be examined with a single pass of the UAV asset. To
 643 overcome this issue, the k-Means clustering algorithm is employed, aiming to
 644 group the center points of smaller individual problematic regions and lead to
 645 a more manageable number of destination points. Focusing on an autonomous
 646 operation, the number of clusters k is selected automatically in the range $[2, 10]$
 647 based on the maximization of the Calinski-Harabasz score [13]. Furthermore,
 648 to acquire more meaningful results, a weighted clustering approach is selected,
 649 where the cluster centroids are calculated with respect to the size of each area.
 650 Figure 9(c) illustrates the outcome of the k-Means clustering. The acquired
 651 cluster centers are forwarded to the site-specific missions module, as the points
 652 of interest where a further on-spot examination will be conducted. Moreover,
 653 the ability to fine-tune or exclude destination points is provided to the user,
 654 to create a more tailored site-specific mission that meets his requirements.

655 As mentioned in subsection 3.2, the employment of RGB-based indices
 656 aims to compose a low-cost and flexible framework. However, note that the
 657 presented approach for the identification of the problematic areas can be ap-
 658 plied in the case of multispectral indices without any modifications and thus,
 659 it can be considered a “plug-and-play” solution.

660 4 Site-Specific Mission

661 Towards assessing the aforementioned problematic locations, a site-specific
 662 mission focused on the detected points of interest is designed. The main ob-
 663 jective of this mission is to provide a more thorough inspection of these individ-
 664 ual spots of the examined area that seem to be problematic in terms of plant
 665 health and provide valuable information to the end-user. To efficiently mon-
 666 itor these individual spots, visual footage from lower altitudes and different
 667 camera angles is captured aiming to visually detect crop health deterioration
 668 sources, such as weed plants, to enable site-specific treatment.

669 4.1 Hot-Point Mission

670 From the motion planning perspective, visiting each of the individual points of
 671 interest can be deduced to the problem of finding the shortest path that visits
 672 all nodes (Figure 9(c)). For ease of understanding, let us assume that the crop
 673 health indicators (VIs) of section III extract k points of interest $\{1, 2, \dots, k\}$
 674 each of one is expressed as $\chi_i = \{Lat, Lon\}$, where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$. Overall,
 675 the set of points of interest is defined by the following equation:

$$\chi := [\chi_1, \chi_2, \dots, \chi_k] \quad (11)$$

676 At this point, the path planning problem is formulated into the *optimal*
 677 round trip that will guarantee the shortest possible route while passing through
 678 all points, only once. For individual coverage, we applied the Travelling Sales-
 679 man algorithm (TSP) [7], which is renowned for finding the shortest path
 680 within an undirected graph. The pseudo-code for monitoring each χ_i is given
 681 in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 2 Hot-Point Mission³

Input: takeoff/landing $\{Lat, Lon\}$, χ , r , φ
Output: An *optimal* circular path around points of interest

- 1: $V[0] \leftarrow$ takeoff/landing waypoint ▷ Starting/ending
- 2: **for each** $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ **do**
- 3: $V \leftarrow \{(Lat, Lon) \mid (Lat, Lon) \in \chi_i\}$ ▷ Create fully connected graph
- 4: **for each** $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ **do**
- 5: **for each** $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, k\}$ **do**
- 6: $E \leftarrow \{(i, j, \|\chi_i - \chi_j\|.meters)\}$ ▷ Distance between points of interest
- 7: TSP \leftarrow TSPSolver(V, E) ▷ TSP solution [7]
- 8: count \leftarrow 0 ▷ Enumerate Hot-Points
- 9: **for each** $\chi \in$ TSPSolver **do**
- 10: $Hot-Point[count] \leftarrow \{(Lat, Lon) \mid (Lat, Lon) \in \chi\}$
- 11: $CenterPoint \leftarrow Hot-Point[count]$ ▷ Define center
- 12: count \leftarrow count + 1
- 13: **for** ($\vartheta \in 0^\circ, 360^\circ$, $step = \varphi$) **do** ▷ $\varphi \in (0^\circ, 360^\circ)$
- 14: $Hot-Point[count] \leftarrow$ Generate points uniformly within a circular region with the
 analogous ϑ and a given radius r around $CenterPoint$.
- 15: count \leftarrow count + 1
- 16: Halt when circle is formed.
- 17: Halt when takeoff/landing waypoint is encountered again.

682 Given the takeoff/landing point and the overall set χ , in lines 1-6, we
 683 treat the defined points as an undirected stationary graph representing each
 684 point within the examined area as a vertex. The distance between each pair
 685 of vertices is defined by the weight of their corresponding edge.

686 In line 7, by solving the TSP algorithm an *optimal* path that visits every
 687 vertex is defined. In lines 9-10, every point - vertex of the resulted *optimal*
 688 path is labeled as *Hot-Point*. As a next step (lines 11-15), we generate a set
 689 of m additional points with an angle $\vartheta \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$ and a constant radius r
 690 around a specified *Hot-Point*. Note that, the number of points m that enclose
 691 a *Hot-Point* depends on an angle φ (line 13) which determines the angular
 692 distance between any two consecutive points on the perimeter of the circle.
 693 The smaller the value of φ , the greater the number of points on the perimeter
 694 of the circle. Figure 10(a) illustrates an indicative example of a circular flight
 695 that encircles a *Hot-Point*.

³ <https://github.com/CoFly-Project/Waypoint-Trajectory-Planning>

Fig. 10: An *optimal* circular path around points of interest.

696 Based on Algorithm 2, the UAV will perform a fixed radius cycle around
 697 the central points of interest (*Hot-Points*) as it follows the resulted path of
 698 the TSP algorithm as sketched in Figure 10(b). It should be highlighted that
 699 the resulting path starts and ends at a specific vertex (line 1) which denotes
 700 the takeoff/landing waypoint after having encountered all the other vertices
 701 of the graph, exactly once. Moreover and if needed, during the execution of
 702 the mission, the user can also use the physical remote control to modify the
 703 speed, heading, and altitude of the aircraft.

704 4.1.1 A *Hot-Point* approximation study on flight time for UAVs

705 This study aims to estimate the UAV's mission time and analyze its association
 706 with the number of points of interest. For the evaluation study, 10 χ sets are
 707 used. Every set includes a different number of distinct points of interest. For
 708 each set, 100 simulation experiments, with a random-shaped distribution of
 709 points of interest, were performed within an area of 10.77 acres (Figure 10(b)).
 710 All sets were executed with a fixed radius r of 5 m and an angle $\varphi = 45^\circ$. The
 711 simulations were carried out with a fixed altitude and speed of 10 m and 3
 712 m/s , respectively. The overall performance of Algorithm 2 in terms of covering
 713 time regarding each set of χ is presented in Figure 11.

Fig. 11: Hot-Point Experimental Data. A box plot visualization of the data distribution for a given set χ concerning the estimated flight time to serve a Hot-point mission.

714 According to Figure 11, each of the sets χ indicates that the estimation
715 coverage time varies and depends on the geographical location (latitude, lon-
716 gitude) of each of the points of interest within the field. Although, the key
717 outcome of this study is that the developed algorithm, for each of the 100
718 simulations, achieves a persistent coverage of 3-30 points of interest within
719 an estimation coverage time close to the average flight time of most common
720 commercial UAVs, i.e. 25-30 min. Such a feature is of paramount importance,
721 as it supports trajectories for covering a large number of individual spots while
722 concurrently respecting the average energy efficiency of a conventional UAV.
723 Note that, the *Estimated Flight Time* on the y-axis could be achievable only
724 if the user does not intervene during the execution of the Hot-Point mission.
725 However, when users use the remote controller to adjust the flight status of
726 the UAV, covering time is increasing or decreasing proportionally to the dura-
727 tion of each action. As a result, the Hot-Point mission as a feasible approach
728 for site-specific inspection can be applied to precision agriculture practices
729 for automated visual footage focusing on low-cost smart farming by utilizing
730 common commercial UAVs.

731 4.2 High Level Semantic Information Extraction

732 During the Hot-Point mission, a closer inspection by the end-user of the prob-
733 lematic field areas is enabled through the captured visual footage. Yet, artificial
734 intelligence can be employed to automate this process and compose the basis
735 of a decision support system. Towards this direction, a weed detection module
736 is deployed to analyze the visual data collected during the Hot-Point mission
737 and provide information regarding the detected weeds to the end-user.

738 Accurate weed detection is a crucial, yet challenging, task of precision agri-
739 culture in order to maintain the health of the overall crop and minimize the

740 damage through selective treatment. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs)
741 have reported remarkable results in a wide variety of computer vision tasks and
742 especially in the fields of object detection [46] and semantic segmentation [42].
743 The proposed framework employs these techniques for the task of weed de-
744 tection. In specific, the particular module is based on DeepLabv3+ [14], a
745 robust deep-learning model for image semantic segmentation possessing state-
746 of-the-art results on PASCAL VOC 2012 dataset [18]. Contrary to more naive
747 approaches of image classification where the input image is classified as a weed
748 or not, the semantic segmentation approach enables the detection of multiple
749 instances and types of weeds by applying a pixel-wise annotation on the input
750 and thus, provides accurate information regarding the location of the detected
751 weeds. The developed module is capable of semantically segmenting weed in-
752 stances depicted on input RGB images captured during the site-specific mis-
753 sion and thus, provides critical high-level information regarding the location
754 of detected weeds to the end-user in order to schedule counteractions on the
755 spot.

756 4.2.1 Dataset

757 It is important to note that weed detection is a quite challenging task due to the
758 nature of the problem since the captured weed instances present a wide variety
759 in terms of form, size, and shape. Moreover, the development of a meaningful
760 dataset that can enclose the majority of different occasions is not an easy
761 task, since it requires an extreme amount of man-hours and the corresponding
762 workforce, as well as the collection of data over a wide period of time. Yet,
763 to train and evaluate the deployed model, a custom dataset was designed
764 for the task of weed semantic segmentation, as an initial approach to create
765 the required challenging dataset. Towards this direction, a set of 1280×720
766 RGB images was collected during real-life experiments over a cotton field.
767 The acquired images depict crop rows of cotton plants where different types of
768 weeds interfere among the planting lines. The annotation of the collected data
769 was conducted by field experts utilizing the LabelMe annotation tool [50].
770 The annotation process led to a set of 201 labeled images where depicted
771 weed clusters are labeled as “weed” while the rest of the image is annotated
772 as “background”. The developed dataset [31] is publicly available ⁴ to the
773 research community. To further demonstrate the challenging nature of the
774 specific task, Table 4 presents the number of pixels for each class, among the
775 number of depicted weed instances contained in the built dataset. As expected,
776 the developed dataset is imbalanced due to the complex nature of the problem.

777 The developed dataset was split into a training (80%) and a testing (20%)
778 set. The splitting process was repeated 3 times aiming to create subsets with
779 different class distributions in order to conduct a more thorough evaluation of
780 the employed detector.

⁴ <https://github.com/CoFly-Project/CoFly-WeedDB>

Class	# Pixels $\times 10^6$	# Instances
Background	175	-
Weed	9	383

Table 4: Number of pixels & instances per class contained in the custom-built dataset

781 4.2.2 Train & Evaluate

782 The deployed DeepLabv3+ instance was pre-trained on PASCAL VOC 2012
 783 dataset and further trained on the previously described, custom dataset for the
 784 weed semantic segmentation task. The model was trained for 500 epochs with
 785 a batch size of 12 on a GeForce RTX 2060 Super GPU. As an optimization
 786 algorithm, Adam solver with a learning rate equal to 10^{-3} was selected. To
 787 tackle the imbalance issue among the dataset classes, focal loss was employed.
 788 Moreover, data augmentation techniques were utilized to enhance the gener-
 789 alization ability of the model. In specific, every input image of the training set
 790 was horizontally/vertically flipped and randomly resized on a scale between
 791 0.5 to 1.5 times of the initial size with a chance of 50%. Finally, a patch-sized
 792 320×320 pixels were randomly cropped from the original image before being
 793 fed to the model, to further augment the training data.

794 The developed weed detector is trained and evaluated on the three different
 795 dataset splits, while its efficiency is measured in terms of Intersection-over-
 796 Union (IoU), a standard accuracy measure for semantic segmentation tasks. In
 797 Table 5 the IoU for each class among the overall mean-IoU (mIoU) is reported.
 798 Results imply that the deployed model is capable of correctly classifying the
 799 samples of background class with significantly high accuracy for all splits.
 800 Regarding the weed class, the accuracy is lower mostly due to the reduced
 801 number of samples in the dataset. Yet, one can consider the reported model
 802 performance satisfying by taking into consideration that for the weed detection
 803 task it is adequate to detect a wide region where weed clusters are present,
 804 compared to other applications of semantic segmentation, such as autonomous
 805 driving, where a crisp prediction of the detected object shape is required.

	Background	Weed	mIoU
Split 1	95.44	44.93	70.18
Split 2	95.83	43.49	69.66
Split 3	96.62	43.96	70.29

Table 5: Model accuracy in terms of IoU (%)

806 5 System Integration

807 5.1 Graphical User Interface

Fig. 12: CoFly GUI, showing the available flight settings menu bar on the left, and the map with the polygon drawn by the user.

808 All of the aforementioned services are packed inside an end-to-end preci-
809 sion agriculture platform called CoFly. The CoFly software is designed with
810 the user workflow in mind to provide him with an interactive environment
811 based on precision agriculture applications. The primary goal is to make scan-
812 ning, imaging, and parametric analysis of crops easy and accessible via the
813 user interface⁵ (UI) (Fig. 12). These functionalities are adequate for most sim-
814 ple missions that require surveillance of a new crop, analysis of photometric
815 indices, and detection of intrusive plant species. To finalize the CoFly software
816 as an integrated end-to-end platform, the connection between the autonomous
817 navigation system, the remote sensing control system, and the graphical user
818 interface is essential to ensure stability in such a large-scale application. The
819 communication of data among different modules is implemented by a Restful
820 API Service [40] which allows the different sub-systems to connect and inter-
821 act with each other by retrieving the necessary data for their execution. Data
822 transmission between sub-systems is done via .json files which contain all the
823 necessary information needed to run any operation of the overall system. Fig-
824 ure 13 illustrates the overall CoFly workflow along with the communications
825 among its modules. It must be emphasized that each and every sub-system of
826 Figure 13 is integrated with the CoFly UI.

⁵ <https://github.com/CoFly-Project/cofly-gui>

827 A video demonstration illustrating the sequence of events among all the
 828 aforementioned services is attached to the following link⁶

Fig. 13: An overview of the CoFly system workflow illustrating the information exchanged among its modules.

829 5.2 CoFly-to-UAV bidirectional communication system

830 For attaining a drone mapping project defined by the GUI, the coverage and
 831 inspection tasks are executed by forwarding the objectives of the correspond-
 832 ing mission to the UAV. As an intermediate communication layer between the
 833 CoFly software and the UAV, a smartphone that runs a mobile application
 834 is connected to the UAV's onboard controller. Towards this direction, in this
 835 paper, to accommodate a common commercial UAV, a custom android app
 836 adaptor has been developed with the use of the DJI API, as a data transceiver
 837 between Algorithm 1 & 2 with the UAV (as shown in Figure 14). This appli-
 838 cation is responsible for forwarding the path to the UAV as well as gathering
 839 information (telemetry, photographs, statuses, and mission logs) and trans-
 840 mitting them to the backend of the platform.

⁶ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C0hdCu-ZRQk&ab_channel=CoFlyProject

841 Note that the aforementioned android application has been set up to provide
842 i) a high level of autonomy for the missions and ii) a dynamic visualization
843 of the flight data. Based on this logic, the interaction between the user and the
844 CoFly software can be done entirely from the GUI, with no need to directly
845 control the UAV with the controller or the smartphone application. Therefore,
846 as the mobile application also works as an on-the-field pilot by allowing
847 to monitor live the mission, the user can take control and directly operate the
848 UAV, if needed. Note that according to the type of the UAV and its functional
849 requirements, a different plugin as an intermediate communication layer might
850 be required (see Adaptor in Figure 13).

Fig. 14: Custom-developed android application adaptor.

851 6 Real-life experiments

852 This section presents two real-life experiments, where the proposed CoFly
853 application was used to monitor, acquire data, and assess the vegetation health
854 of real agricultural fields. The experiments were conducted in the fertile land of
855 the Thessalian plain and more specifically in a rural area planted with cotton
856 located in the city of Larissa, Greece. The functionalities and technologies
857 of the CoFly software, as well as the produced results, were evaluated by the
858 experienced agronomists of the Bios Agrosystems S.A.⁷, who specialize in crop
859 production, soil control, and soil management. This section aims to evaluate
860 the robustness and efficiency of the CoFly software in real-world precision
861 agriculture operations.

⁷ <http://www.bios-agrosystems.gr/en-US/>

862 6.1 Experimental Setup

863 For the real-life experiments, a commercial UAV (DJI Phantom 4 Pro) equipped
864 with an RGB camera was used for image acquisition. The UAV flight planning
865 for monitoring and inspection was done by the developed algorithm 1 and 2,
866 respectively. For mission control, an android smartphone device (Xiaomi Mi
867 Max 2) was used to run the android app adaptor, described in section 5.2.
868 Finally, a portable 4G router (tp-link M7350) was used as an intermediate
869 communication layer between the smartphone and the CoFly software. To
870 evaluate the efficiency of the proposed framework, two scenarios were consid-
871 ered. The first scenario was performed in July 2019 during the first stages
872 of plant growth, while the second scenario was performed in September 2019
873 during the ripening period, when the cotton fibers had appeared. The main
874 objectives of these two experiments were to (i) identify the optimum flight
875 envelope to acquire the best data and provide an orthomosaic as an accurate
876 map of the field, (ii) extract plant health information (VIs) that could give
877 indications on the year’s harvest and cotton’s growth stage (timeline view)
878 and (iii) detect the existence of weeds in a specific site of crops. In the next
879 subsections, each experiment is analyzed and distinguished according to the
880 flight date and cotton’s developmental phase.

881 6.2 Mid-summer

882 As to the first scenario, the cotton field during its early stage along with the
883 calculated path is depicted in Figure 15. To demonstrate the practical enforce-
884 ment of the proposed navigation algorithm (Algorithm 1) in terms of avoiding
885 NFZs/Obstacles, we considered an area within the original field as restricted,
886 meaning that the UAV is not allowed to fly above. For coverage mission (see
887 Table 6), the selected *flight altitude* and *scanning density* resulted in a spatial
888 level resolution of 90%. In addition, the operational speed was selected to be
889 3 m/s, which is low enough to maintain the quality of the collected images,
890 and the gimbal pitch was selected to be -90°(meaning that the camera is al-
891 ways in the “top-view” mode), an angle that calibrates images for 2D map
892 outputs. Figure 15 graphically illustrates the resulted path as calculated from
893 Algorithm 1. A direct outcome is that the path-planning algorithm managed
894 to efficiently alter the UAV path to meet the field characteristics. More specifi-
895 cally, path (i) completely covers the area of interest, (ii) does not contain
896 bootstrapping (path crosses), and (iii) carefully avoids the NFZs.

Mission	Coverage						Inspection	
	Flight altitude (m)	Scanning density (m)	Flight direction (°)	Speed (m/s)	Corner radius (m)	Gimbal pitch (°)	r (m)	φ (°)
Mid-summer	30	18	30	3	0.5	-90	5	45
Early-autumn	50	15	30	3	0.5	-90	-	-

Table 6: Mission details corresponding to Algorithm 1 & 2 for monitoring and inspection tasks.

Fig. 15: Calculated coverage path for mid-summer mission.

897 The acquired images during the conducted mission are forwarded to the
 898 knowledge extraction module for further processing. Initially, the orthomosaic
 899 is calculated and presented in Figure 16(a). It can be noted that the collected
 900 data are sufficient to create a high-resolution map of the examined agricultural
 901 area, implying the robust operation of the developed path planning module.
 902 In Figures 16(b)-16(e) the image representations of the calculated VIs are pre-
 903 sented. The calculated VIs can provide a crisp overview of the crop's health,
 904 indicating areas with relatively poor vegetation conditions. Finally, in Fig-
 905 ure 16(f) the result of the points of interest detection module is illustrated
 906 for the VARI index. One can see that the implemented module can efficiently
 907 detect problematic, in terms of vegetation health, field regions where the site-
 908 specific mission should be deployed.

909 Given the geolocation of the depicted points of interest, Algorithm 2 was
 910 deployed to provide a site-specific inspection as illustrated in Figure 17(a).
 911 Additional information corresponding to the Hot-Point mission for the inspec-
 912 tion task can be found in Table 6. In Figure 17(b) qualitative results from
 913 the site-specific mission in the aforementioned areas are presented. It is noted
 914 that the deployed weed detector can sufficiently detect regions where weed
 915 instances are depicted. The advantage of a semantic segmentation approach is
 916 also illustrated in the results since accurate spatial information regarding the

Fig. 16: Results of the knowledge extraction module from the experimental evaluation conducted on mid-summer.

Fig. 17: Designed (a) site-specific mission and the corresponding (b) weed detection module output over the acquired visual footage. In (a) the take-off/landing area is notated with the black marker while in (b) the detected weeds are highlighted with light red color.

917 existence of weeds in the field can be provided to the end-user through the
 918 selected approach.

919 6.3 Early-autumn

920 As to the second scenario in the early autumn, the cotton field during its
 921 boll and fiber maturation along with the calculated path is depicted in Figure
 922 18. Note that the selected aspects of navigation for the coverage task were
 923 adjusted to achieve a spatial level resolution of 90%, while the UAV's altitude
 924 was set to be 50m (see Table 6).

Fig. 18: Calculated coverage path for early-autumn mission.

Fig. 19: Results of the knowledge extraction module from the experimental evaluation conducted on early autumn.

925 In Figure 19(a) the extracted orthomosaic of the examined area is pre-
 926 sented. Similarly to the previous case, the designed path enables the collection
 927 of sufficient data to provide a detailed overview of the field. Figures 19(b)-

928 19(e) illustrate the calculated VIs, pointing out regions where the vegetation
929 conditions are poor. Finally, in Figure 19(f) the key outcome of the problem-
930 atic areas detection module is demonstrated for the VARI index. It should be
931 noted that the specific experiment was conducted in early autumn, a period in
932 which cotton is harvested and the cotton plants are fully developed. Thus, any
933 interfering weeds are covered by the foliage of the cotton plants and cannot
934 be visually detected by an above inspection. Furthermore, the treatment of
935 weeds can be considered an off-season activity during this time period, since
936 it is more crucial to conduct it at the early stage of the crop's life cycle when
937 the dominance of crop plants over the weeds is crucial. Towards this direction,
938 the site-specific mission for weed detection was not executed in this case.

939 7 Conclusions

940 UAV systems innovation is valuable in agriculture. Following leading-edge
941 technologies, in this paper, an end-to-end and low-cost precision agriculture
942 platform based on a fully functional autonomous UAV system has been pro-
943 posed. In contrast to the majority of the already existing agriculture platforms,
944 which use cloud-based approaches for processing agricultural data and estab-
945 lishing prices according to the information processing, the proposed platform
946 has been designed to provide offline and real-time at the field's edge, stand
947 counts, and assessments. Towards that purpose, coverage, and inspection mis-
948 sions for any type of UAV are developed to provide plant health maps, weed
949 measurements, and detection by owning an integrated deep learning module.

950 All of these capabilities are packed inside an end-to-end platform function-
951 ing on mobile devices including high-level user commands and proper data
952 representations that ease the utilization of UAVs in precision agriculture ap-
953 plications.

954 The functionality of the proposed system was tested and validated with
955 extensive experimentation in agricultural fields with cotton in Larissa, Greece
956 during two different crop sessions i) in mid-summer and ii) in early autumn.
957 In both experiments, CoFly preserved all the desired features of common agri-
958 cultural software, while at the same time, it achieved fully autonomous inspec-
959 tion tasks empowering the UAV robots also as a tool for site-specific precision
960 farming. This feature is of paramount importance in agribusiness, as it can be
961 utilized in information procurement, examination, and consistently observing
962 fields by the farming community to acquire contemporary field management
963 skills. CoFly software with a low budget provides beneficial and high accuracy
964 insights to turn into the critical segments of the farming industry.

965 As future directions, we are interested in evolving this research by integrat-
966 ing multi-UAVs for monitoring and inspection tasks. In such an approach, the
967 proposed agricultural software should be enriched with a multi-robot decision-
968 making scheme to autonomously navigate each robot to perform individual
969 coverage subtasks according to the overall set of the user's objectives. This
970 work may examine more complicated scenarios where UAVs will also perform

971 pesticide spraying treatments to have a robust system tailored to a variety of
972 agricultural applications.

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981 **Declarations**

982 Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

983 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or
984 personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported
985 in this paper.

986 **Code & Data Availability**

987 The overall precision agriculture platform along with the corresponding mod-
988 ules and the dataset generated during the real-life experiments are open-source
989 and available in the <https://github.com/CoFly-Project> repository.

990 **Author Contributions**

991 E. K. Raptis contributed to the material preparation, UAV data collection,
992 analysis, conceptualization, writing - original draft, visualization, and soft-
993 ware. M. Krestenitis contributed to the material preparation, conceptualiza-
994 tion, data curation, writing - review editing, visualization, and software.
995 Graphical user interface and integration were performed by K. Egglezos and
996 O. Kypris. L. Doitsidis and A. Ch. Kapoutsis did the supervision, project ad-
997 ministration, writing - review editing. K. Ioannidis, E. B. Kosmatopoulos,
998 S. Vrochidis, and I. Kompatsiaris performed the supervision, resources, and
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Consent to participate

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